

**POLICY
ANSWERS**

D2.4

Report on Foresight Findings

Main author: Simon Winter (born Schmitz)

Responsible organisation: DLR-PT

Date: 24 February 2025

 <https://www.facebook.com/WBInfoHub>

 <https://x.com/wbinfohub>

 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/wbinfohub/>

www.westernbalkans-infohub.eu

POLICY ANSWERS is funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe project "R&I POLICY making, implementation ANd Support in the WEsteRn BalkanS", Grant Agreement N° 101058873.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Contributing authors

Work Package

Due date

Submission date

Current version

Dissemination level

doi

Julia Schmälder (DLR)

WP2 Monitoring for Agenda Setting

30 June 2025

28 February 2025

24 February 2025

Public

[10.5281/zenodo.14914058](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14914058)

Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Contributors	Description
v0.1	25.11.2024	Simon Winter (born Schmitz)		Workshop planning and results of the regional foresight workshop in Podgorica
v0.2	11.12.2024		Ulrike Kunze (DLR), Elke Dall (ZSI)	Comments by WP lead and coordinator
v0.3	24.02.2024	Simon Winter (born Schmitz)		Additional revisions updating references, adding further Annexes
v1.0	24.02.2024		Elke Dall (ZSI)	Formatting for submission

Disclaimer

POLICY ANSWERS is funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe project "R&I policy making, implementation and support in the Western Balkans", Grant Agreement N° 101058873. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union (EU) or the European Commission (EC). Neither the EU nor the EC can be held responsible for them. For further information regarding POLICY ANSWERS visit www.westernbalkans-infohub.eu

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1 From Scenarios to Recommendations on Anticipatory R&I Policies in the Western Balkans ..	7
1.1 Strategic Foresight and how it can benefit R&I policies in the region.....	7
1.2 The 2023 co-creative anticipatory science advice Workshop	8
1.3 Beyond the Horizon: A Joint Foresight Exercise at the 2024 EU-Western Balkans Ministerial Meeting	12
1.4 Disseminating the Findings of the Foresight exercises in the WB	13
2 Annex	15
2.1 Impressions from the Foresight Workshop	15
2.2 Trend cards used at the Foresight session of the EU-WB Ministerial Meeting in Skopje	16
2.3 The three scenarios as a basis for the Anticipatory Science Advice Workshop in Podgorica	39
Scenario 1: Joining the Common Market	39
Scenario 2: Looking beyond EU borders.....	42
Scenario 3: Putting Business First.....	46

List of Figures

Figure 1: The benefits of strategic foresight.....	7
Figure 2: Workshop design at a glance.....	9
Figure 3: Foresight-Card with recommendations elaborated in March 2023 in Podgorica. Page 1	10
Figure 4: Foresight-Card with recommendations elaborated in March 2023 in Podgorica. Page 2	11
Figure 5: Trend card examples (see Annex for all Trend cards).....	13
Figure 6: Impressions from the Podgorica Foresight Workshop in March 2023 in Podgorica	15

Executive Summary

This report outlines the processes and results of the Task T2.4 “Foresight and agenda setting”, which was led by the partner DLR, with contributors from IMP and all Western Balkans (WB) partners. Building on the foresight exercise for the WB region carried out in 2020/21, a workshop on Strategic Foresight brought together policymakers and other stakeholders from the region in March 2023 in Podgorica. In a concerted initiative, experts from the WB implemented foresight tools and methods and used them to discuss, identify, and prioritise the policy actions that work towards the most desirable aspects of the future scenarios outlined in the study “Strategic Foresight in the Western Balkans” (2020/2021). Using a so-called backcasting method that helps determine the actions needed to pave the way for these desired reforms, the workshop generated strategic science advice from and for the region related to the mapping of priority themes of common interest.

Together with the experts, input for a joint Policy Brief on the results of the workshop was elaborated in cooperation with Task T2.5.

Furthermore, an additional Foresight-Workshop was organised as side event for the EU-Western Balkans Ministerial meeting in Skopje in September 2024 (in cooperation with Task T1.3 “Ad-hoc policy coordination meetings”). At the Foresight session, R&I experts from the region discussed pressing trends in R&I as well as their implications on policymaking in the region.

1 From Scenarios to Recommendations on Anticipatory R&I Policies in the Western Balkans

1.1 Strategic Foresight and how it can benefit R&I policies in the region

Strategic Foresight is a methodology that prepares policy-makers and R&I stakeholders for the unforeseen by harnessing collective intelligence to anticipate and prepare for change. Rather than predicting the future, it explores potential futures, their opportunities, and challenges. This structured framework empowers governments and organizations to identify, anticipate, and adapt to future shifts, hurdles, and prospects. In the R&I context, Strategic Foresight reveals future opportunities and shapes robust policies and strategies. It helps anticipate emerging technological, societal, and market trends, enabling organizations and governments to shape innovations proactively. By exploring different scenarios, it uncovers untapped potential, inspires creative thinking, and helps organizations adapt to remain competitive. Developing a Foresight mindset, or "Futures Literacy," ensures the long-term relevance and impact of R&I efforts.

How can policy makers and R&I stakeholders in the WB use Strategic Foresight?

Policy makers and R&I stakeholders in the Western Balkans can use Strategic Foresight to systematically explore and identify trends, anticipate innovations, niches, and seize emerging opportunities for investment and policy-making. Foresight moreover enables the development of robust strategies, effective resource allocation, and informed decision-making. Furthermore, it can foster collaboration between stakeholders and builds resilience to future disruptions (see Figure 2). By embracing this forward-looking methodology, the Western Balkans can position itself as a dynamic and adaptable region in the global landscape.

Figure 1: The benefits of strategic foresight

The following handbooks on Strategic Foresight provide in-depth explanations on the methods of Strategic Foresight and concrete orientation on how to use them:

- Global Centre for Public Service Excellence: Foresight Manual - Empowered Futures¹
- Government of the UK: Futures toolkit for policy-makers and analysts²
- United Nations Futures Lab: Strategic Foresight Guide³
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP): UNDP RBAP Foresight Playbook⁴

1.2 The 2023 co-creative anticipatory science advice Workshop

On 13 and 14 March 2023, the POLICY ANSWERS partners DLR-PT, Institute Mihajlo Pupin and STP of Montenegro gathered a diverse group of R&I experts from all WB economies as well as from the RCC and the UNDP in Podgorica (Montenegro). Based on the available three scenarios and the science advice of the European Commission's study "Strategic Foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the Horizon" (2022)⁵, the dialogue on potential futures provided stakeholders from the region and beyond in a Workshop with a platform to exchange views, define joint priorities and plan strategic R&I approaches. 20 selected participants from all WB economies chose the most desired outcomes of the respective scenarios and identified R&I policy priorities. These were then coupled with the formulation of measurable targets and tangible actions to meet them. It is important to note that the recommendations drafted as outcome of the Workshop have been elaborated solely by the R&I experts in the region. The POLICY ANSWERS team facilitated the workshop and the compilation of the recommendations in this document.

The Workshop's methodology

The workshop followed a six-step approach to prioritising research and innovation (R&I) policies in the Western Balkans (WB). First, three scenarios for R&I in 2035 were presented and participants were divided into groups to analyse each scenario (see Annex 2.3. for the scenarios). This step is useful as it encourages participants to think long-term and to consider different possible futures, thus promoting creative and strategic thinking. In the second phase, participants prioritised aspects within their assigned scenario, which were then combined to identify three to five overarching R&I policy priorities. This step is valuable as it helps to distil the most important elements from different scenarios, ensuring that the resulting priorities are comprehensive and forward-looking. These priorities formed the basis for the formulation of objectives in the third phase through a plenary discussion. This step is crucial as it allows for collective input and consensus building, ensuring that the objectives reflect the shared vision of all participants.

The fourth phase involved a World Café format, with each table focusing on one objective. Participants rotated between tables, contributing ideas and suggestions for concrete actions to

¹ Global Centre for Public Service Excellence. (2018). Foresight Manual - Empowered Futures for the 2030 Agenda. United Nations Development Programme. <https://www.undp.org/publications/foresight-manual-empowered-futures>

² Government Office for Science. (2024). Futures toolkit for policymakers and analysts. GOV.UK. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/futures-toolkit-for-policy-makers-and-analysts>

³ UN Futures Lab. (2023). UN Strategic Foresight Guide. UN Futures Lab. <https://un-futureslab.org/project/un-strategic-foresight-guide/>

⁴ United Nations Development Programme. (2022). UNDP RBAP Foresight Playbook. UNDP Asia-Pacific, <https://www.undp.org/asia-pacific/publications/undp-rbap-foresight-playbook>

⁵ European Commission. (2022). Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the Horizon, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5ddd1971-2a64-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>. doi: 10.2777/202437

achieve the goals. This step is beneficial as it encourages cross-fertilisation of ideas and allows participants to contribute to multiple objectives, resulting in a more holistic and interconnected set of actions. In the fifth stage, the group prioritised the proposed actions. This step is essential as it helps to focus resources and efforts on the most impactful and feasible actions, thereby increasing the likelihood of successful implementation. The sixth and final phase was to look at the details of the goals, including timelines, funding sources and responsibilities. This step is critical as it transforms abstract goals into actionable plans and assigns clear ownership and resources, which is essential for effective implementation of R&I policies.

Figure 2: Workshop design at a glance

The Workshop’s results: Anticipatory science advice

The results of the workshop are summarised in a Foresight Card (see below). The recommendations were presented to the ministers at the 2024 EU-Western Balkans Ministerial Meeting.

Strategic Foresight

Recommendations for the future of R&I
in the Western Balkans

May 2023

Anticipatory science policies need to embrace the emerging trends in R&I that the study "Strategic Foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the Horizon" identified. Based on these signals of change, experts from the region recommend to further strengthen the scientific ecosystem in the Western Balkans in order to avert undesirable aspects of the scenarios of the future accordingly:

1. Foster National Innovation Systems in the Western Balkans

Expected outcome

Knowledge-based economies & sustainable economic growth

Potential implementation activities

- In a quadruple helix dialogue, stakeholders can define the thematic development and transformation instruments in the field of innovation, technology transfer and Smart Specialisation.
- Jointly define the thematic development and transformation instruments in the field of innovation, technology transfer and Smart Specialisation, involving the stakeholders in a quadruple helix dialogue.
- Address legal gaps at the national level to improve the legal basis for innovation activities.
- An appropriate balance between competitive projects and institutional funding would be a favourable approach for systems where demand for R&D is still limited.
- In order to protect new technical solutions, researchers and companies in the Western Balkans should promote a culture of intellectual property protection, initiating protection procedures prior to market release or other public availability.

2. Further develop Human Capital

Expected outcome

Well-trained students and experts that effectively respond to market developments, diverse educational formats, and networks with the diaspora

Potential implementation activities

- Build on existing good practice of dual education in the region.
- Policy makers, academia and industry should ensure a continuous dialogue, including with invited experts (OECD, EU, etc.) to discuss framework conditions, learning methods and human capital development.
- Establish a Regional Innovation Academy, which aims to provide entrepreneurs and innovators with essential skills to bring creative research ideas to the market, with a series of training focused on disruptive fields, support from foreign experts on funding and legal issues, and the opportunity to further strengthen innovation networks in the Western Balkans.
- Stimulate regional exchange programmes between young researchers and innovators with industry and academia, allowing them to acquire valuable innovation and strategies and skills.

3. Establish a strategic R&I cooperation platform for industry and academia

Expected outcome

The adoption of a legal framework that supports collaboration between industry and academia, facilitating sustainable networks that increase private investments in R&D and initiate early-stage venture capital funds for disruptive industries

Potential implementation activities

- Organise serial events at a regional level that facilitate the quadruple helix interaction to promote the mutual understanding of R&D collaboration, resource sharing and concrete approaches for joint action through training, meetings, panel discussions and workshops.
- Establish a networking initiative to map and foster a continuous exchange between the different R&I platforms existing in the region, identify gaps and coordinate joint projects to learn from each other.
- Initiate effective funding instruments for start-ups and SMEs in the region. The establishment of dedicated programmes could be supported by regular foresight exercises.

Figure 3: Foresight-Card with recommendations elaborated in March 2023 in Podgorica. Page 1

Strategic Foresight

What is Strategic Foresight?

Strategic Foresight helps to prepare for the unexpected. It uses collective intelligence in a structured and systematic way to anticipate developments and better prepare for change. Foresight is not about predicting the future but about exploring different plausible futures that could emerge and the opportunities and challenges they present.

Strategic Foresight is a methodology that helps governments and organisations to identify, anticipate and adapt to future changes, challenges and opportunities. It provides a structured framework for analysing current trends, identifying potential future scenarios and developing strategies to prepare for them.

How is the POLICY ANSWERS project using Strategic Foresight?

Prevailing challenges in the Western Balkans show that the orthodox approaches of the past to preparing for the future have not always produced the desired results. Translating ambitious political agendas and goals into concrete results, therefore, requires new, innovative approaches.

The POLICY ANSWERS team facilitated a Foresight Workshop on Anticipatory Science Advice, where selected experts from the region exchanged visions and defined joint priorities for R&I. The workshop was based on the three co-created scenarios of the study [Strategic Foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the Horizon](#), which are entitled "Joining the Common Market", "Looking beyond EU Borders", and "Putting Business First". The summary of the recommendations for R&I of the future reflect the priorities of the participants and were elaborated during a workshop in Podgorica in March 2023.

Figure 4: Foresight-Card with recommendations elaborated in March 2023 in Podgorica. Page 2

1.3 Beyond the Horizon: A Joint Foresight Exercise at the 2024 EU-Western Balkans Ministerial Meeting

In cooperation with task T1.3 of POLICY ANSWERS (“Ad-hoc policy coordination meetings”), the POLICY ANSWERS team organised a second Foresight Workshop. In the first part, participants learned about the benefits and importance of Strategic Foresight and anticipatory decision-making. In the second part, participants themselves used the method of working with trends of the futures until the year 2035. Herein, they experienced the implications of these trends on their day-to-day work and life.

Concretely, they rotated among four sets of standing tables. On each of the table groups, they found a stack of a pile of trend cards. Participants were then invited to draw 3 trend cards from the pile and work with these trends. Each table had a different task what could be done with the trend cards: “Dream Big”, “Prioritise”, “Invent”, “Connect the Dots”.

The benefits of working with the trend cards included:

1. **Developing a shared understanding of trends:** The trend cards can help workshop participants develop a shared understanding of the major forces shaping the futures. By exploring and discussing these trends together, participants can gain a deeper appreciation of the complexities and interconnections of different future developments and trends.
2. **Encouraging creativity and innovation:** The trend cards can inspire creative thinking and help participants imagine new possibilities for the future. By using the cards to explore different futures and possibilities, participants can generate new ideas and approaches that may not have been considered before.
3. **Enhancing strategic thinking:** By using the trend cards to explore potential future developments, participants can further strengthen their strategic thinking skills. They can consider how different trends may interact and affect their government, and use this information to develop more robust R&I initiatives.
4. **Improving decision-making:** The trend cards can help participants make better decisions by providing a framework for considering the potential impact of different trends on their R&I organisation or institution. By considering the potential long-term consequences of different decisions, workshop participants can make more informed and effective choices.
5. **Fostering collaboration and communication:** The trend cards can be used as a tool for fostering collaboration and communication among workshop participants. By working together to explore different futures and ideas, participants can build stronger relationships and develop a shared vision of potential futures, which might be especially beneficial in the WB.

Approach in detail

The workshop approach was inspired by an engagement tool developed by Sitra, a renowned institution for Strategic Foresight. The trend cards presented various trends already influencing R&I ecosystems and our daily lives, shaping the future. Rather than predicting the future, these cards stimulated participants' thinking, broadening their perspectives and inspiring new ideas about the future of R&I in the WB.

Each table had a distinct task and approach to working with the trend cards. At the start of each round, every table randomly selected three trend cards.

1. **Table: Dream Big** This table encouraged participants to envision ambitious and innovative ideas, pushing the boundaries of R&I. Using the trend cards as inspiration, they explored bold concepts and futuristic scenarios.

2. **Table: Prioritise** At this table, participants focused on identifying the most critical trends and their potential impact on R&I. They prioritised the selected trends based on their relevance and urgency, considering their implications for policymaking and strategic planning.
3. **Table: Invent** This table stimulated creativity and innovation. Participants were challenged to develop new products, services, or solutions based on the selected trends. They explored how these trends could be leveraged to address societal challenges and create opportunities for economic growth.

Table: Connect the Dots At this table, participants aimed to identify connections between different trends and explore potential synergies. They sought to uncover emerging patterns and insights that could inform future R&I strategies and initiatives.

Figure 5: Trend card examples (see Annex for all Trend cards)

The trend cards used in the workshop were sourced from several authoritative studies, including:

- European Commission's study "Strategic Foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the Horizon"⁶
- Regional Cooperation Council Study "Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans"⁷
- ESPAS "Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future"⁸

These sources provided a sound basis for trends shaping the futures of the R&I ecosystems in the WB and Europe more broadly.

1.4 Disseminating the Findings of the Foresight exercises in the WB

Strategic Foresight is not yet part of the governance culture in the WB. As a modest contribution to raising awareness of its methods and benefits, members of the POLICY ANSWERS team used the regular **Steering Platform meetings** to update representatives on the progress, results and planned activities of the foresight exercise. An **interview** with the Task Leader of T2.4 promoted

⁶ European Commission. (2022). Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the Horizon, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5ddd1971-2a64-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>. doi: 10.2777/202437

⁷ Regional Cooperation Council. (2023). Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. <https://www.rcc.int/pubs/178/unleashing-the-potential-for-competitiveness-trends-in-the-western-balkans>

⁸ European Strategy and Policy Analysis System (ESPAS). (2024). Global Trends to 2040: Choosing Europe's Future. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/global-trends-2040-choosing-europe%E2%80%99s-future-0_en. doi:10.2760/816783

on the **Western Balkans Info Hub** presented the approach of the task and how Strategic Foresight methods could be used for more anticipatory policy making.

The results of the European Commission's 2021 Strategic Foresight report and the POLICY ANSWERS task have fed into the **Regional Cooperation Council (RCC)** study "[Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans](#)". The study, prepared by DLR-PT on behalf of the RCC, presents trends likely to shape the region's competitiveness up to 2035. It examines the potential impact on inclusive growth and offers possible implications of the trends that could be useful for the WB.

Instead of organising a virtual workshop as originally planned, the POLICY ANSWERS team decided to organise a face-to-face **Foresight Workshop** in the framework of the **EU-Western Balkans Ministerial Meeting in Skopje** in September 2024 (see above). Here, the results of Task T2.4 on Anticipatory Science Advice were presented to many WB Ministers in the form of a Foresight Card (see Annex). The Card outlines the recommendations developed by the R&I experts from the WB and summarises how Strategic Foresight methods can be useful for R&I policies.

2 Annexes

2.1 Impressions from the Foresight Workshop, Podgorica in March 2023

Figure 6: Impressions from the Podgorica Foresight Workshop in March 2023 in Podgorica

2.2 Trend cards used at the Foresight session of the EU-WB Ministerial Meeting in Skopje

The following trend cards were developed by DLR-PT for an interactive Foresight workshop at the EU-WB Ministerial Meeting in Skopje in September 2024.

For more information on the method of Strategic Foresight and the use of these trend cards for anticipatory R&I policy-making, feel free to reach out to Dr. Julia Schmälder or Simon Winter from the POLICY ANSWERS team

(Julia.Schmaelter@dlr.de; Simon.Winter@dlr.de)

EU Accession

The path to EU accession for the Western Balkans remains uncertain, with competing priorities and enlargement fatigue among current EU members. The recent candidacies of Ukraine, Moldova, and Georgia further complicate the timeline, affecting the region's regulatory environment, investment climate, and market confidence, which could stall reforms and slow economic integration with the EU.

Political Volatility

Ongoing political instability in the Western Balkans, marked by unresolved regional conflicts and governance issues, is creating an unpredictable environment. This volatility deters long-term investment, complicates business planning, and undermines economic growth, while political uncertainty delays reforms and hinders economic integration both within the region and with the EU.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Weak Culture of Compliance

Weak compliance with EU standards in the Western Balkans, particularly in areas such as anti-corruption, rule of law, and institutional integrity, continues to be a challenge. Poor law enforcement and perceived corruption undermine fair competition and discourage investment, while slow progress in judicial independence and institutional reform complicates efforts to create a transparent, predictable business environment.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Declining Population, Rising Workforce

The Western Balkans are experiencing a demographic shift with a declining overall population but an increasing proportion of working-age individuals. This trend presents both challenges, such as a shrinking domestic market, and opportunities for a more competitive labor market. Effective policies focusing on education, employment opportunities, and talent retention are crucial to leverage this demographic advantage.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Western Balkans as Nearshoring Destination

The Western Balkans are emerging as an attractive nearshoring destination for European companies, thanks to their proximity, competitive wage levels, and skilled labor force. As companies seek to reduce supply chain risks and maintain greater control over production, this trend is likely to boost employment, attract foreign investment, and stimulate economic growth, positioning the region as a critical hub for European manufacturing and services.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Western Balkans as Friendshoring Destination

The trend of 'friendshoring,' which involves relocating supply chains to politically and economically allied countries, could lead to increased EU investment in the Western Balkans, particularly in economies that align closely with EU values and policies. However, countries with closer ties to Russia or China may see a reduction in European investments as EU companies prioritize partnerships with more politically aligned and stable markets.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Increasing Intra-Regional Trade in Services

Intra-regional trade in services within the Western Balkans is increasing significantly, driven by initiatives like CEFTA and the Common Regional Market Action Plan, which have reduced trade barriers, harmonized regulations, and improved infrastructure. This trend is fostering greater economic integration, enhancing resource allocation efficiency, and creating new business opportunities.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Boost in Backward Spillovers

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in the Western Balkans is increasingly focusing on higher value-added activities, such as technology and research-intensive industries. This shift enhances the potential for backward spillovers, where local firms benefit from knowledge and technology transfers from foreign investors, leading to improvements in productivity, innovation, and the development of more sophisticated industries.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Competing Incentive Structures

The Western Balkans have successfully attracted FDI through various incentive structures, such as tax breaks and special economic zones. However, competition among the region's economies to offer better incentives may lead to a fragmented investment environment. This 'race to the bottom' could reduce the region's overall attractiveness to foreign investors, limiting sustained FDI growth and undermining efforts to create a unified, competitive market.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

FDI Shift from WB to Ukraine

The post-war reconstruction of Ukraine could divert Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) away from the Western Balkans, as investors seek opportunities in Ukraine's larger market and strategic position within European supply chains. This shift, driven by reconstruction funds and Ukraine's geopolitical significance, may challenge the Western Balkans in attracting and retaining investment, potentially weakening the region's economic prospects and competitive position.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Digital Transformation of the Labor Market

The digital transformation of the labor market in the Western Balkans is accelerating, with increased adoption of AI, machine learning, and online platforms. While this shift offers opportunities for growth, it also highlights a significant digital skills gap. To fully benefit, the region must invest in upskilling its workforce to meet the demands of a digital economy.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Growing Skills Gap

The Western Balkans face a growing skills gap, especially in digital and technical fields. This is driven by inadequate investment in education, outdated curricula, and the emigration of skilled workers. As the demand for new skills rises with the twin transition to a digital and green economy, the region risks falling behind if it cannot equip its workforce with the necessary competencies.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Skills Mismatch Between Labor Supply and Demand

The misalignment between education systems and labor market needs in the Western Balkans is contributing to a growing mismatch where many young people are overqualified for available jobs, while key industries face skilled labor shortages. This ongoing trend is limiting job opportunities, hindering economic growth, and exacerbating youth unemployment.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Labour Emigration

Labor emigration continues to deplete the Western Balkans of its skilled workforce, as workers seek better opportunities abroad due to low wages, limited job prospects, and high corruption levels at home. This trend exacerbates the skills gap and weakens the region's human capital, posing significant challenges to economic development and competitiveness.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Diaspora Potential

The Western Balkans have a large diaspora that represents a significant, yet underutilized, resource for regional development. While there are efforts to engage the diaspora in knowledge transfer, investment, and business partnerships, these are often hampered by weak institutions and a lack of trust. Effectively tapping into the diaspora's potential could greatly enhance the region's economic prospects.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Youth Unemployment

Youth unemployment remains a critical issue in the Western Balkans, with rates significantly higher than in the EU. The region's young population faces a mismatch between education and labor market needs, limited job opportunities, and insufficient support for entrepreneurship. High youth unemployment not only stifles economic growth but also risks social instability as young people become disillusioned with their prospects.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Twin Transition

The Western Balkans are undergoing a twin transition toward a greener and more digital economy, driven by global demand for sustainable solutions and the need to comply with EU standards. Successfully navigating this transition can open new markets, particularly in agriculture, energy, and digital trade, while also improving alignment with broader European economic trends.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Demand for Private Investment

The Western Balkans urgently need more private investment to support innovation and economic growth. Public funding alone is insufficient, and the lack of venture capital and private equity is a significant barrier. Attracting more private investment is essential for fostering a dynamic and competitive business environment, particularly for SMEs looking to scale up and innovate.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

R&D Systematically Underfunded

The persistent underfunding of research and development (R&D) in the Western Balkans compared to EU levels continues to limit the region's capacity for innovation. As public research institutions struggle with limited resources and insufficient funding, the region faces ongoing challenges in driving technological progress, developing new products and services, and strengthening its overall innovation ecosystem.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Scattered Collaborations Between Academia and Business

Collaboration between academia and industry in the Western Balkans remains fragmented and limited. Despite growing efforts to promote these partnerships, the lack of strategic coordination continues to hinder the region's potential for innovation and weakens its competitive edge.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Underused potential of Smart Specialization Strategies

Smart Specialization Strategies can significantly boost competitiveness in the Western Balkans by focusing on areas of regional strength and fostering innovation-driven growth. Several economies are developing the Strategies, identifying priority sectors such as sustainable agriculture, energy, and manufacturing. Effective implementation and financing of these strategies can promote innovation, enhance regional economic integration, and better align the region with EU innovation goals.

*Schmitz & Schmälter (2023): Unleashing the Potential for Competitiveness: Trends in the Western Balkans. Regional Cooperation Council.

Insufficient Support for International SME Cooperation

The Western Balkans recognize the importance of internationalizing SMEs for economic growth and innovation. However, this recognition has not been fully translated into actionable support. To boost international cooperation, the region needs stronger policies, better institutional frameworks, and initiatives that remove barriers and enhance the business environment, enabling SMEs to benefit from global opportunities.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021.

Fragmented Digitalisation

Digitalization is a key driver of change in the Western Balkans, but its benefits are unevenly distributed. Inadequate digital infrastructure, especially in rural areas, and a lack of digital skills contribute to fragmented digitalization across the region. Economic inequalities, underperforming higher education, and urbanization trends are likely to exacerbate this fragmentation, hindering comprehensive digital transformation.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021.

Deepening Integration into Global Value Chains

Global Value Chains (GVCs) are increasingly integrating international production, trade, and investment. For the Western Balkans, this presents an opportunity to strengthen their global competitiveness. To position themselves effectively in GVCs, the region must identify competitive advantages, invest in emerging sectors, and develop innovative solutions that align with global market demands.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021.

Declining Infrastructure

The infrastructure in the Western Balkans, both physical and digital, continues to face significant challenges. Ongoing low fiscal capacity, weak institutions, and poor regional coordination remain major obstacles to long-term investment. Political tensions further impede the development of the infrastructure necessary for a fully integrated regional economy.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021.

Growth Disparities

Economic and infrastructure development in the Western Balkans is often concentrated in capital cities, leaving smaller towns and rural areas behind. This creates significant growth disparities within the region. As clusters of excellence and innovation develop, these disparities may widen, driving further urbanization and uneven regional development.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021. DLR Projektträger

Slow Reforms on Energy Transition

Among others, the European Commission's "European Green Deal" will introduce reforms that seek to accelerate the clean energy transition. While the Western Balkans are bound by international commitments such as the Paris Agreement, to date, few far reaching policies have been implemented. Not investing in a transition towards greener energy options might have high economic costs until 2035 and beyond.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021. DLR Projektträger

Shift Towards Green Economy

A Green Economy focuses on sustainable growth driven by investments that reduce carbon emissions, enhance energy efficiency, and conserve biodiversity. For the Western Balkans, key areas include sustainable waste management, green entrepreneurship, eco-friendly tourism, and conservation projects. These initiatives are already influencing the region's development and hold significant potential for future growth.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021. DLR Projektträger

Rising Economic Damage from Climate Change

The economic impact of climate change is increasing across the Western Balkans, with billions of euros in damage already recorded in agriculture alone. As extreme weather events become more frequent, other key sectors like forestry, fisheries, and tourism are also facing growing threats, disproportionately affecting this climate-vulnerable region.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021. DLR Projektträger

Strategic Importance of New Technologies

The adoption of digital tools, AI, and advanced manufacturing is becoming increasingly critical for the Western Balkans. Early adoption and customization of these technologies are driving innovation, boosting productivity, and opening new markets, particularly in agriculture, education, and energy. This trend is essential for enhancing regional competitiveness.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021.

Slow RD&I Growth and Technology Diffusion

Research, Development, and Innovation (RD&I) in the Western Balkans is progressing slowly, which limits the region's ability to capitalize on new growth opportunities. The slow pace of technology diffusion hampers economic progress, but Smart Specialization Strategies offer potential pathways to address these challenges and accelerate innovation.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021.

Changing Demographics

Population decline is accelerating in the Western Balkans, with significant reductions expected in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Albania, and Serbia by 2050. This demographic shift poses serious challenges to pension systems, healthcare, and labor markets, making it increasingly difficult for companies to attract and retain talent.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021. DLR Projektträger

Rising Youth Entrepreneurship Amid Limited Government Support

Youth entrepreneurship is on the rise in the Western Balkans, spurred by the transition of many SMEs from first to second-generation ownership. However, the region still lacks sufficient government-led programs to foster entrepreneurial spirit and support startups, potentially limiting the full realization of this trend.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021. DLR Projektträger

Underperforming Educational & Vocational Sector

The educational and vocational sectors in the Western Balkans are underperforming, as highlighted by the OECD's PISA assessments. The region's ability to build a well-performing, innovative economy is at risk if education and training systems do not improve to meet the demands of a modern workforce.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021. DLR Projektträger

Limited Career Opportunities for Researchers

Career opportunities for researchers in the Western Balkans remain limited, with few high-level academic positions available and a generally low reputation of the academic sector. This trend is contributing to the region's struggle to retain talent in research, development, and innovation.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021. DLR Projektträger

Demand for Open Government

There is a growing demand for more open and participatory government across the Western Balkans, despite high levels of corruption. While most economies in the region have joined the global Open Government Partnership, the effectiveness of these initiatives is still limited, and citizens are increasingly calling for greater transparency and inclusion in policymaking.

*European Commission, DG Research and Innovation, Strategic foresight in the Western Balkans: Recovery on the horizon, Publications Office of the EU, 2021.

The Centrality of Geopolitics

The trend from global cooperation to increased competition and fragmentation continues, with new threats emerging in areas like hybrid warfare, disinformation, and cyberspace. In the Western Balkans, this could manifest as heightened political tensions, increased vulnerability to external influence on media and elections, and challenges in cybersecurity, e.g., complicating the region's EU integration and stability.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

Economic Challenges

Geopolitical fragmentation and the transition to climate neutrality are creating new threats to global economic growth. The sustained rivalry between the US and China, along with emerging regional blocs, will likely reshape global trade relations. For the Western Balkans, these shifts may result in economic uncertainty, making it harder to attract investment and integrate into global supply chains, while also navigating the transition to net-zero industries.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

Environmental & Climate Crises

Climate change is accelerating, accompanied by widespread environmental degradation. The world is likely to overshoot the Paris Agreement targets, increasing the risk of climate tipping points. The Western Balkans, with its diverse ecosystems and reliance on agriculture, is particularly vulnerable to climate impacts, such as extreme weather events and biodiversity loss, which could exacerbate socio-economic challenges and migration pressures.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

Rising Use of Fossil Fuel

Global energy consumption is rising, and so is the use of fossil fuel – despite the increasing share of energy generated by renewables and their falling costs. The pace of the green energy transition may be slowed by investments in fossil fuels, critical mineral shortages, and limited electric grid capacity. The energy transition is likely to benefit some more than others and could open up new arenas of geopolitical competition, and social tensions within countries.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

The Quest for Equality

Inequalities are growing in importance and complexity. Beyond economic inequalities, access to education, technology, healthcare, infrastructure, climate justice or intergenerational fairness are becoming increasingly relevant. In the EU and Western Balkans, these inequalities could exacerbate societal tensions, fuel political polarization, and weaken democratic institutions.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

Technological Acceleration

The pace of technological deployment is accelerating, with increasing convergence across sectors. This is happening alongside rising expectations for technology to drive the green transition, amidst geopolitical rivalries and regulatory challenges. In the Western Balkans, rapid technological change may widen the digital divide, pose regulatory challenges, and create both opportunities and risks for economic development and labor markets.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

Managing Health

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the need for well-resourced health sectors and underscored global interconnectedness, while widening the gap between rich and poor. The health sector will continue to be a driver of scientific and technological innovation. New treatments and therapies could bring huge dividends, while challenges such as anti-microbial resistance require close attention.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

Changing Living Conditions

People are increasingly living in cities and are more exposed to the negative impacts of climate change. Technologies are changing the way we work and learn, bringing both opportunities and risks. On the one hand, there are new ways of working and delivering services; on the other, there are job losses and a pressing need for new skills. Both climate change and the twin digital and green transition will have strong and diverse impacts across the EU and Western Balkans.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

Threats to Democracy

The trend towards democratic backsliding continues. Democracies are facing sustained attacks on their freedoms, including efforts to undermine elections, media independence, and judicial integrity. In the Western Balkans, these threats could manifest through increased political polarization, external interference, and challenges to governance, potentially slowing down democratic reforms and EU integration efforts, while destabilizing the region's political landscape.

*based on ESPAS (2024): Global Trends to 2040 - Choosing Europe's Future. European Strategy and Policy Analysis System

2.3 The three scenarios as a basis for the Anticipatory Science Advice Workshop in Podgorica

Scenario 1: Joining the Common Market

“The Western Balkans are part of Europe and not just a stopover on the Silk Road”, said former President of the European Commission Ursula von der Leyen 15 years ago in her first State of the Union address. Today, in 2035, her quote can be seen as the starting point for the WB accession into the EU and a period of rapid and transformative change for the Western Balkans. **Eventually, Albania, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia gradually became members of the EU until 2035 although with some transitional provisions.** Bosnia and Herzegovina and Kosovo have also taken a great leap forward towards the EU, but there are still some political barriers which hold back the EU accession. In terms of socio-economic implications, the influence of the EU in the region has increased significantly and it has slowed down the economic presence exerted by third countries (e.g. China) in comparison to the 2020s. The free trade among the four new EU members with the rest of the Union has been further developed on various levels, and the Union as a whole remains the most important trading partner for the entire WB region.

The implementation of the Copenhagen Criteria⁴ has significantly improved the openness and transparency of the WB’s governance and thereby led to increasingly effective public administrations. The domestic, regional political and ethnic conflicts from the past, which were pre-dominantly perceived as origins of stagnation and an encrusted political system, have been jointly swept under the carpet. In its latest Western Balkans report, the international NGO *Transparency International* (TI) highlighted the ongoing and, in some areas, successful fight against corruption - one of the biggest challenges in the region in the last 50 years. These reforms have also affected the R&I sector: Education, R&I have been anchored (to varying degrees) in the political agenda of the WB by planning and implementing systemic changes towards building knowledge-based societies and evidence-informed policy making.

One example of the increased impetus for reforms is the handling of Open Science and Open Access: Research publications and data as well as (newly built) R&I infrastructures are openly accessible for domestic and foreign partners. The majority of the publicly funded WB initiatives and projects within national, regional and international R&I competitions have been evaluated in a transparent manner by international, independent peer reviewers in 2035. Moreover, in the last 15 years, the WB have taken a number of anti-corruption steps, such as adapting legislation and establishing dedicated anti-corruption institutions with both preventative and effective law-enforcement competences. These efforts as well as the increased national public R&I investments have contributed to decreasing the level of corruption in research and higher education, according to TI’s *Corruption Perceptions Index*. Media outlets and civil society especially have promoted and supported the anti-corruption developments in these fields and have contributed to a renewed trust in the academic system in the region.

Improvements can also be noted in the research infrastructure and the cooperation between academia and the private sector. The development in both areas was significantly supported by a better exploitation of the European Framework Programmes and the innovation support measures offered by the EU. The number of R&I projects, international publications and innovation clusters initiatives have doubled in the last decade. University reforms and the additionally gained research openness have significantly improved the impact and relevance of WB researchers in the global scientific arena during

the last 15 years. The anti-corruption measures as well as the stronger focus on applied research activities in the universities and the public research sector have positively affected the international reputation and social acceptance of scientific work in the WB. Nonetheless, the application of the academic curricula of leading universities in accordance to the market and entrepreneurship needs is still an ongoing process.

Propelled by the increased collaboration within the EU in the field of innovation, special attention is nowadays devoted to entrepreneurship and SMEs. This has resulted in an advanced entrepreneurial culture in the WB. The change in attitudes towards entrepreneurship has likewise ameliorated the status of Research, Development & Innovation (RD&I) in general and thereby helped to improve the cooperation between universities and SMEs in the WB. The national governments have increased their attention devoted to support programmes for SMEs and have considered a public investment in strengthening SME development. As a consequence, a substantial number of spin-offs have taken place in the WB. SMEs also benefited from the internationalisation and closer connection with the diaspora and business communities in Europe. Especially the cooperation with some national and European Centres of Excellence in the field of ICT, health and green technologies have led to the development of concrete products, as called for by some foreign investors.

The collaboration with the business sector has stimulated the private financing of R&D conducted at public universities and research organisations. Nevertheless, according to the *Eurostat R&D Financial Report 2034*, the business enterprise investments in the new EU members Albania, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia were on average still significantly lower than the R&D funding from entrepreneurship in the EU27 countries. Furthermore, the World Economic Forum's "*Regional Risk of Doing Business*" 2034 edition still cites concerns about prevailing corruption in the business sector - despite some recent positive trends. Nowadays, major companies exert great pressure and influence on political parties and found legal loopholes to avoid public scrutiny and accountability mechanisms. A representative survey conducted by the Regional Cooperation Council (RCC) in 2032 found that "the prevailing nepotism" and "clientelism" were cited as the most important reasons for youngsters to pursue a job in a different country than their home-country.

The adoption, implementation and enforcement of the EU *Acquis Communautaire* on Environment was an obligation for aspiring member countries in the framework of the stabilisation and association process. Upgrading infrastructure and developing a much bigger and more competitive industrial base in this field were (to a various extent) political priorities especially in the EU member countries of the Western Balkans in the last decade. In terms of economic reforms, the WB radically adjusted their stance vis-à-vis renewable energy. The potential of biomass, hydropower, wind, and solar was supported through improved cooperation and exchange with European enterprises, research institutions and state actors, as well as significant funding through the European Commission's *Green Deal Just Transition Mechanism*. The European Commission's *Energy Cluster Initiative*, established in 2023, further supported this change in attitude. Due to the high investments in green technologies, the British weekly newspaper *The Economist* praised the Commission's support mechanisms for renewable resources "[...] as yet the green transition's most effective instruments of the last decade".

The increased R&I public investment, especially through the support of several EU initiatives and programmes, has radically changed the energy sector in the WB. The newly built infrastructures have created new job opportunities, and the educational and vocational sector with the support of EU funding was able to improve the quality of education and digitalisation in terms of acquiring specialisations in the fields related to the green transition. In this context, the swift towards knowledge-intensive

services, especially in the field of green technologies, has progressed. Nevertheless, the technology penetration, even in prioritised industries sectors, lags behind the global average. During the latest *Western Balkans Summit “EU Green Future”* in 2033, the Commissioner for Energy and Environment welcomed the joint initiative *“Together for our society”*. Brought together by a common cause, the WB had agreed on transnational standards by adopting specific technical innovation related to the everyday life of individuals in the region.

Due to the increased scientific research excellence and the improved infrastructures, the competitiveness and productivity of the WB’s economies have significantly risen as it was stated in the latest edition of the World Economic Forum’s *Global Competitiveness Report*. All of the WB have entered the top 70 of the ranking. The digitalisation of important sectors such as public administration, health and education improved significantly the value added. Nevertheless, some challenges prevail. Starting from a relatively similar economic structure, regional economic specialisation was comparatively slow over the last 30 years. However, the specialisation of the four WB which had become members of the EU for certain product markets have been accelerated by the European commitment to become the world’s first climate- neutral continent by 2050.

The EU company law rules cover issues such as the formation, capital and disclosure requirements, as well as operations (mergers, divisions) of companies. These regulations are relevant for all member states - respectively also for Albania, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia. The aim is to enable businesses to be set up and to carry out operations anywhere in the EU. Indeed, many traditional WB companies, especially medium-sized family companies, were forced to shut down as they were unable to meet these EU regulations and compete with EU peers.

As stated in the WB Prime Ministers’ Joint Declaration at the latest WB summit in July 2034, the freedom of movement in the EU has contributed to change the brain-drain of well-educated professionals into a brain circulation even if plenty of expatriates have not returned to the Western Balkans yet. Generally, the academic freedom is increasingly seen as a positive sign for the scientific immigration to the region. The implementation of sustainable science- industry cooperation and knowledge transfer have offered new perspectives for career development. This applies especially to scientific areas in which the WB are specialised in.

A positive side effect of this evolution is the region’s R&D improved attractiveness to incoming researchers. However, a sustainable strategy for brain gain of R&I foreign experts is still missing in the majority of the WB. There are still WB researchers who are intrigued by the opportunity to emigrate and continue their research in better-paid jobs and more prestigious institutions in the “old” EU countries. Thus, the Prime Ministers acknowledged during the WB summit in July 2034 that concrete incentives for the return of highly skilled workers are still required as the business sector laments shortages of an adequately skilled labour force. For now, companies retreat to recruiting employees from Ukraine, Belarus, and Turkey.

Wildcard: The College of Western Balkans

After her successful International Initial Offering (IPO) of her second start-up, Sofija Popović decided to found a political party that would seek to reform the public sector and reduce administrative burdens to set up a company in Montenegro. Following her landslide win and elevation to power, Popović introduced sweeping public administration reforms and promised “a new generation of civil servants for Montenegro”. Aided by an unnamed philanthropist, Montenegro set up the first National School of Administration in the region in 2031. Inspired by the prestigious French *École nationale d’administration (ENA)* or the College

of Europe, the School attracted motivated talents from across the country, whose majority nowadays predominantly work for the government. The School's approach of organising classes only remotely, moreover played into the hands of the younger generation of the diaspora, who returned to Podgorica upon completion of their degrees.

Whereas advocates of the new School praise the more effective public administration, critics allege nepotism in the choice of students and a perpetuation of influential families in public decision-making roles. Whether the School can serve as a model and create spill-over effects in the Western Balkans will depend on the degree of interference from politics in the curriculum. Popović's main opponent for the forthcoming election in Montenegro already hinted at the fact that he has a different idea on what the mindset and skills of the future for a new generation of civil servants would be.

Scenario 2: Looking beyond EU borders

By 2035 the EU has become increasingly fragmented and economically under pressure due to overall low economic growth rates aggravated by a rise in regional and social disparities. In addition, external shocks have occurred, such as a new influx of immigrants, alarming debt crises in a few of its member states, caused by the bursting of the real estate sector bubble in 2032. Correspondingly, resources were diverted to policy areas such as economic stabilisation and health but also to homeland security, defence as a response to geo-political tensions. Enlargement policy has lost priority, and the budgets for European R&I policy have stagnated at the same nominal level as Horizon Europe, the 9th European Framework Programme for R&I (2021-2027) that ended eight years ago. **In 2035, the enlargement fatigue at the EU side is met by an accession fatigue by the WB, which have grown tired of ever-continuing accession talks.** A perceived double standard between current member states and accession states in terms of good governance requirements did not contribute to pacify EU-sceptics in the WB.

Disintegration tendencies in the region, however, had already existed for several decades, and even the unifying perspective of EU accession began to show clear signs of erosion more than 15 years ago. Many citizens from the WB region grew weary of the prevailing domestic and regional political and ethnic conflicts, which were predominantly perceived as signs of stagnation of an encrusted political system. At the same time, the yearning for change at any price increased. A political scientist from Belgrade expressed the situation as follows in a European television report in fall 2034: "In the last five years, it has become increasingly secondary *what* happened, as long as at least *something* happened that could change the negatively perceived status quo".

Since 2025, the lack of perspective for EU accession in the near future and the resulting geopolitical vacuum has been taken advantage of by Russia, China, Turkey, and the Arab countries and has expanded the United States' influence in the region. All of these governments signed a variety of treaties that removed tariffs for a selection of Balkan goods and boosted trade with the WB. In addition, strategic geopolitical military interests have been brought into play. New military agreements of distinct WB with Russia, the USA and Turkey continue to undermine regional stability and cooperation.

Although free trade with the EU has continued and the EU as a whole has remained the most important trading partner for the WB region, some of the WB firms have been able to diversify their markets and enter niches in global markets. Wine from the region has become an appreciated product among China's vast number of consumers. Initiated by new military agreements, a few Western Balkan companies could profit from subcontracts in military production and related R&D. However, most of the firms did not

succeed in integrating into global value chains (at least not at higher-tier levels) and severely struggle with the growing internationalisation pressure. Imports from China have become cheaper and have replaced domestic production to an even greater extent, especially in the field of machinery and sophisticated chemical products.

The 2034 World Bank Report *Accelerating sustainable productivity growth* notes that a structural shift in the economy towards medium- and high-tech production in the region has been comparatively slow for the past seven years. The shift towards knowledge-intensive services has only been slowly progressing too. This has had implications for a deceleration of the diffusion and mainstreaming of radical technologies in the business. A good example of the low technology penetration that has a growth-inhibiting effect is the green industries sector, whose growth in the WB region lags well behind the global average, despite investments from Chinese companies in selected strategic business areas (renewable energies, material recycling and re-use).

Due to the volatile political situation, foreign direct investments (FDIs) from the EU have declined. They have partially been replaced by FDIs from China, Russia, the Arab countries and Turkey. These investments were mainly made in strategic areas and concerned basic industries (mining, chemicals), the agricultural sector, transportation, infrastructure and construction. European companies have also increasingly sold their shares to overseas investors. This has led the tourism sector, the energy and the telecom utilities sectors to gradually change property to investors from overseas.

Wandering the streets of Sarajevo these days in 2035, one can hear occasional chats not only in Bosnian, but also in Russian and Mandarin. According to data published by the Confucius Institute, the number of students in the Western Balkans that have taken Mandarin language classes have risen steadily since 2026. This trend is representative for isolated additional FDI in education, especially from China, Turkey and the Arab countries. Firstly, these investments concerned extracurricular institutions, such as the aforementioned Confucius Institute. Secondly, further privatisation of the higher education sector was particularly affected. This has led to massive student protests and “sit-ins” in spring 2033, which were generally received by the media as the “Hot Spring”. These protests have soon spread throughout the region, prompting the education ministers of Northern Macedonia, Albania and Kosovo to announce measures to curb further privatisation of the higher education sector and the hollowing out of state universities, respectively. The “Hot Spring” has created spill-over effects to civil society, which took to the streets and expressed their fear that primary and secondary education would also be privatised gradually.

In relative terms, the ICT sector shows the biggest economic success with the greatest growth potential in the region in recent years (until today). Many start-ups have also emerged in this area, which have provided employment for young, creative people - particular in large cities. ICT services have particularly been demanded by the mining and material sector, the energy and the tourism sector. In terms of growth during the last 15 years until 2035, the energy and sustainable tourism sectors have followed the ICT sector at a distance, while the healthcare sector and green industries have even had only marginal growth rates. The provision of digital infrastructure and digital services was primarily driven by private actors, which has led to increasing geographical disparities. While beneficial for urban areas, this has further widened the connectivity gap between rural and urban areas with several negative political, economic, social and demographic consequences. The 2034 UN-Habitat’s Report *Fostering rural development* found that only 13% of youngsters (defined as people younger than 30 years) in the Western Balkans wish to move to the countryside in the next five years.

Starting from a relatively similar structure, regional economic specialisation and Smart Specialisation Strategy processes have developed slowly over the last 30 years, both within individual regions and between the WB. The specialisation dynamics were slowed down by repeatedly introduced protective self-sufficiency measures of individual WB for certain product markets due to swelling political tensions. Consequently, this has triggered temporary bilateral trade restrictions within the region.

The European Commission's *Status Report on ERA-Integration of the WB Region*, which was published last month in September 2034, confirms that R&I policies are not integrated in the overall national strategic priorities of the WB. This low priority is also reflected in mediocre public budget allocations for R&I, which remain overall at a low level. Investments in domestic medium to larger-scale R&I infrastructure are particularly negatively affected. The precarious budgetary frameworks has had a clear negative impact on domestic scientific and technological excellence. Even new collaborations with China and Russia in the field of science could not outbalance the lack of basic material and immaterial domestic resources in the WB.

Due to budget pressures, researchers, especially from some selected technical disciplines, are seeking increased third-party funding, which is why knowledge and technology transfer continues to play an important role. R&D spending by domestic companies and their limited absorption capacities for external R&D supply have, however, increased only slightly. Overall, corporate financing of R&D conducted at public universities and research organisations can neither provide a significant push nor meet the existing demand for financial means by the academic sector.

The association of the WB to the 11th European Framework Programme (EFP) for Research and Innovation, whose first calls were launched in January 2035, is being delayed and there are doubts whether the association will still be successfully concluded at all. Critical voices note that almost the entire WB region has been associated to the FPs for 30 years, but continues to have high subsidy needs. The Innovation Institute, an association of the leading European RTI policy consulting institutes, noted in their yearly report on *Innovation Policy in Europe* that, "the R&I policy reform agenda that has been repeatedly invoked by the European Research Area (ERA) so far had little concrete impact - beyond political lip service - in the WB. Instead of hearty reforms in line with the ERA agenda, too often only single aspects have been reformed or sometimes only cosmetically embellished". In essence, the report insinuates that the ERA has been equated with the Research Framework Programme, which has been primarily regarded as a potentially accessible source of income during the last 30 years, but not as a reform agenda.

One example of the insufficient impetus for reform is the handling of Open Science. Despite past remarkable efforts by policy-makers and researchers in the WB to implement the Open Access agenda in line with the European vision, a sluggishness has taken hold in the course of further implementation. This was partly caused by a lack of financial incentives (e.g. from the Framework Programme). The same development applies to the disclosure of data from publicly funded research projects. After an initial phase of political declarations of intent and, above all, externally funded pilot projects, there was a rapid cooling-off phase. This can partly be explained by the insufficient provision of national funds, which were made available to cover the economies' implementation of the long-term strategic Open Science agenda.

Despite the noticeable disintegration tendencies, cooperation in the field of research with the EU has remained important for the WB due to the existing ties, the ongoing attraction of the EU in R&I and the geographical proximity. National statistical R&D surveys show that the extent of scientific and

technological cooperation with the USA and China is only about half of the S&T cooperation with the EU. Russia and Turkey follow at some distance.

China and Russia in particular are also investing in R&D in the Western Balkans, and a few EU countries such as Hungary continue to show a willingness to invest in foreign R&D in the region. These investments sometimes serve soft diplomacy interests and are used for financing specific professorships but also for the establishment of private universities or colleges. Strategic R&D investments are made in certain industries (mining, agriculture, defence industries) in an attempt to gain economic control. In such areas, pockets of R&I excellence with strong ties to partner institutes in China, Russia or elsewhere could be established.

According to the *New Global Innovation Index* published in Autumn 2024, the region's R&D attractiveness to incoming researchers has stagnated, while brain drain from the WB has severely increased. Some well-qualified workers have taken advantage of the new opportunities for cooperation with China, Turkey, the Arab region and Russia and have migrated to these countries for work. Brain gain, on the other hand, has almost come to a standstill due to the less than favourable job prospects, strong cultural differences and unattractive salary. Experts in the field relate the absence of brain gain in the research sector to decreasing levels of academic freedom in the region. According to the European University Association (EUA), corruption in the higher education sector has worsened in the WB region in recent years. This, in turn, has negatively affected the international reputation and social acceptance of research in and from the WB. Especially NGOs are alerted about this development, but also the huge majority of the academic community feels repelled and increasingly frustrated by such developments. The 2033 OECD's *Government at a Glance*-indicators for public administration reforms underline that in comparison to the 41 OECD countries, the WB score rather poorly in terms of transparency, efficiency, and accountability. Although levels of corruption remain difficult to pinpoint, pressure groups such as Transparency International or CIVICUS lament the comparatively high figures, calling it "endemic for the region".

Wildcard: Introducing the WesternBalcoin

Disenchanted by the stalling EU accession process, the Government of Serbia joined forces with Bulgaria and Hungary and introduced the region's first digital currency, the WesternBalcoin. The currency is administrated by a consortium of the respective national central banks. The joint digital currency shall further improve economic stability and growth, facilitate the trade in goods and services among the participating countries and reduce cross-border administrative burdens for businesses. Eventually, the countries hope to exert greater influence in the global economy.

In order to counter economic volatilities and exchange rate fluctuations, the Heads of States decided to peg the WesternBalcoin to the Chinese e-Yuan, which the People's Republic of China had introduced as early as 2021. Officially, the e-currency does not intend to counter the EU's digital Euro, though economic analysts interpret it as an attempt by the participating countries to further move towards economic and fiscal autonomy from the EU. To date, an official statement let alone a recognition of the e-currency by the European Central Bank is pending.

Scenario 3: Putting Business First

Looking back from 2035, it becomes clear that the “business first”-credo to settle conflicts in the Western Balkans by boosting economic recovery has become the main pathway for multilateral cooperation in the last 15 years. During the 2028 EU-Western Balkan Summit, the WB concluded that institutional reform and regional development is the only way to consolidate their influence in Europe. Economic cooperation was significantly supported by the implementation of the 2022 regional “Open Balkan” agreement and its several follow-ups, which has facilitated free trade and business spill-overs between the Western Balkans.

Although the political disputes at national and regional level continue, the WB governments’ “pro-business attitude” facilitates exchanges and cooperation between various actors in these economies. **The WB continue their efforts to implement the Copenhagen Criteria, but joining the common market is no longer the main political priority in most economies. Lengthy EU-accession negotiations are ongoing with all the WB, though without a political breakthrough on the horizon.** This is also reflected in the absorption fatigue by the WB with respect to the EU’s Instrument for Pre-accession Assistance (IPA). A recent study conducted by the European Commission found that on average around 51% of available IPA funds have been used by the WB. Consequently, the EU member states’ allocation to this instrument was reduced significantly.

Nowadays, the administrative burden on the business sector is low, corporate taxes are minimal, labour unions have limited impact, and digital solutions are supported by the government. Private business interests significantly influence states’ decision-making processes to their own advantage. Despite improvements in the fight against corruption, an oligarchic culture continues to prevail, which negatively affects the research and higher education sectors among others.

Foreign direct investments (FDI), especially in the areas of digital infrastructure, products and services, predominantly comes from EU and European companies. Since 2025, they increasingly originate in the USA, India, Russia and China. The overall size of FDI in R&I has increased in the WB region as well as the R&D expenditures of domestic companies. SMEs have entered international business relations and got involved in higher tiers of international value chains. The way forward is a selective modernisation of some economic sectors (such as energy; ICT; food; construction; healthcare) and specialisation towards key sectors for the regional economy.

Economic modernisation and public sector innovation are supported by EU institutions as well as by the European Investment Bank. Consequently, the region’s start-up scene is prospering. Capital cities such as Belgrade, Tirana and Sarajevo have become regional hubs for pioneering technology. Overall, the WB have seen a sectoral shift towards regional medium-high and high technology products and an increased adoption of more radical technologies in business and consumer applications. The attractive new labour market opportunities in some cities further propel domestic and increasingly also intra-regional mobility and trade.

Despite these positive trends, prevailing corruption in the business sector impedes the WB to achieve their full growth potential. Influential businesses secure their monopolies in the market and use their political leverage to avoid accountability and public scrutiny. As a consequence, the WB are lagging behind their European neighbours according to the World Bank’s Facilitating Business Index. An article by Balkan Insight entitled “The growing wealth gap between Western and Eastern Europe” highlights that the WB are struggling to transform their economic growth to the benefit of their societies at large.

One priority area for public and private investment is digitalisation. The education and vocational training sector reacted to this demand and trains talented youngsters through courses related to ICT, data and other areas demanded by the economy (such as engineering). Although structured top-down reforms of the higher education sector are pending, some faculties (especially from private universities) start to offer tailor-made courses for companies. All administrations from the WB are setting-up R&I agendas that are integrated into overall national priorities. These R&I agendas are implemented through innovation support measures via projects and infrastructures. Science-industry collaboration is promoted through these measures, resulting in more sustainable collaborations between universities and businesses. Additionally, the *Western Balkans Six Chamber Investment Forum*, a joint initiative of chambers of commerce from Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Montenegro, and Serbia, established a regional innovation mechanism that successfully facilitates the advancement of tech-sectors.

The number of subsidiaries of international technology companies opening offices in Belgrade, Tirana and Sarajevo has been growing, which has positively impacted private R&I budgets and infrastructures. This, in turn, has created a more competitive market for private R&I. Universities and research organisations increasingly receive private financing for R&I, especially in the areas of applied research in the Natural Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) domains.

Public R&I budgets have not been increased and as a result basic, fundamental and public research has collapsed. This continues to affect traditionally operating universities most negatively. Scientific research excellence has increased due to private investments, although only in domains relevant for business R&D and for addressing human capital needs. Researchers from the WB take part in EU R&I initiatives and programmes more frequently, often with co-funding from businesses. This has strengthened the networks of researchers and resulted in additional funding for research activities. Through these networks, a limited number of agile universities and research organisations were able to attract strong foreign researchers for domains relevant to businesses thanks to investments in domestic medium to large-scale R&I infrastructures that are open to or shared with businesses. Despite the growing number of private R&I companies, opportunities for researchers remain limited and brain drain continues to be a major challenge in all WB. Engineering-focused universities experience a great loss of expertise because their researchers increasingly move to the flourishing private high-tech or ICT sectors to pursue a career there.

Effects of the desperately needed reforms in the science system are starting to take hold. Driven by international trends in the science system and EU goals, many publicly funded R&D project results and publications are published with open access (although not all), public research data is more widely shared and open peer review is predominantly applied. Due to more openness, and increased frequency in science-business collaboration, scientific work has gained an overall positive reputation in society. Although corruption in research and education continues to exist, it has diminished considerably due to the frameworks imposed by internationally operating businesses. Simultaneously, the increase in private R&D and the lack of funding for basic and fundamental research has implicitly affected academic freedom in research and teaching. Businesses who sponsor positions, institutes and research programmes have gained influence on research and education programming and strategies, limiting individual academic freedom and causing occasional conflicts of interests.

While successfully supporting business development and promoting exploitation of natural resources, most of the WB countries have not implemented reforms in areas such as rule of law, education, and social policy. Demand from the EU as well as from civil society on green investments has grown and the

local population demands environmentally friendly practices. Massive protests in Serbia in 2030 put a stop to the plan to open a new coal mine. However, ambitious transformative reforms regarding climate mitigation and the transformation towards a green economy have been largely absent. Climate change, air pollution and resource exploitation severely impact all economic sectors equally. Only those industries, where a clear market opportunity was available and quick wins could be attained (e.g. renewable energies; waste water/recycling industries), read the signs of the time and adapted to these challenges. Today, these opportunity-driven sectors are technologically proficient and are early adopters to serve the needs of the local and regional market. Even though businesses still exploit natural resources, recent years have also seen increased investments in the development of green technology, as world-wide there is a clear demand for more sustainable products. For regional impact, it is however important to have successful green technology adopted by industry, government and citizens in the WB - requiring investments that businesses see not reflected in short-term revenues and many citizens cannot afford.

The absence of long-term investments in social and public infrastructures has led to increased tensions, especially between urban and rural regions in terms of supply of public services and labour market opportunities. Serbia and Montenegro have invested in technological parks outside of urban areas boosting developments, but capacity of such facilities is limited by the lack of infrastructure and human capital in these areas. Social unrest is present in several WB, and policy-makers do not offer solutions to address these issues. EU accession negotiations are therefore not progressing as foreseen.

ABOUT POLICY ANSWERS

POLICY ANSWERS (R&I POLICY making, implementation ANd Support in the WEsteRn BalkanS) supports policy coordination in the Western Balkans and with the EC and the EU. 14 partner organisations, representing network nodes in the region and EU expert organisations, support policy dialogue through formal meetings (such as ministerial and steering platform and ad-hoc policy meetings), monitoring and agenda setting, capacity building and implementation of the EU's Western Balkan Agenda, as well as the alignment of thematic priorities. The project implements regional pilot activities and offers an information hub based on the westernbalkans-infohub.eu online information platform. The partners provide analytical evidence via monitoring and mapping activities of the stakeholder ecosystem, of the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda and of the Western Balkans' integration into the European Research Area as well as via strategic foresight. POLICY ANSWERS also allows for tailored and targeted capacity building activities in the Western Balkans as well as regional alignment of priorities in relation to the digital transformation, the green agenda and towards healthy societies. Pilot activities provide learning opportunities on policy and programme level and reach out to final beneficiaries related to improved academia-industry cooperation, researcher mobility, inclusion of youth in policy processes, promotion of research infrastructures and increased innovation skills in all areas.

